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Research Article

**TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS TO EVALUATE ITS
RECENT INCREASE IN POPULATION AND ITS ECONOMIC
EFFECT****Usama Abdul Jabbar, Syed Akbar Raza Sherazi, Rabia Babar**
Shaikh Zayed Medical Complex, Lahore**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Type 2 diabetes is a constant disease. It has been spreading gradually throughout the universe. As the consequence of its prevalence it has become a contagion in some nations. Many persons are affecting from diabetes now a days. The prevalence of diabetes will become twice in the coming years. This is because of enhancement in the number of persons in the coming years which will create more trouble for the physicians and clinics. The Cochrane Database of Systemic Review provides necessary information for this research. World health organization and American Diabetes Association gives the basis of transmission and identification. Proper cure of the diabetes is not present still. The effects of disease can be reduced by improving the living conditions, cure of fatness etc. Disease can be cured by chemicals like non-sulfonylurea secretagogues, thiazolidinediones, and insulin etc. In 2006, insulin was permitted to use for the treatment of the diabetes mellitus.

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Corresponding author:**Dr. Usama Abdul Jabbar,**
Shaikh Zayed Medical Complex, Lahore

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INTRODUCTION:

The most ancient disorder found in men is diabetes mellitus. About 3000 years ago, it was seen first time in Egypt. The clear-cut identification between type 1 and type 2 diabetes was made in 1936. In 1998, diabetes type 2 was defined as the constituent of metabolic disorder. The most frequent type of diabetes mellitus is the type 2 diabetes mellitus. The most significant features of the diabetes type 2 were opposition of insulin, hyperglycemia and comparative insulin shortage. The factors that cause the diabetes type 2 include the hereditary, ecological and performances¹.

Type 2 diabetes showed various complexities which are either shorter or longer duration of time. It causes the mortalities in some patients too. Type 2 diabetes showed deaths of the most of the sufferers because it is the most common type of diabetes. It can be identified after longer time in under progressed states.

Epidemiology:

In 2011, 366 million individuals were suffering from diabetes mellitus. In 2030, this amount will be enhanced up to 552 million. The number of patients of diabetes mellitus are enhancing in each nation. 80% cases of diabetes are present in under developed or developing countries. In 2011, 4.6 million individuals died because of diabetes mellitus. Because of surroundings and living strategies, the chances of diabetes mellitus in population varied among various countries².

In Africa there is little information present about the spreading of diabetes. Some examination made in Africa showed huge increase in the diabetes in both country and municipal areas. It affects both males and females equally. In Africa the most common diabetes is diabetes mellitus type 2. Only 10% cases of diabetes type 1 were reported. In THE US an observation was made in 2010 according to which 25.7 million cases of diabetes type 2 were identified. 90-95% cases of diabetes type 2 were seen in US. In the recent studies diabetes type 2 is mostly affecting the young patients. It is more widely spreading in progressing states. The ages of the diabetic patients mostly lie between 90-95%.

Way of life, inheritance and clinical situations:

The main reasons of diabetes mellitus are way of life and inheritance. Many ways of life are significant which are important in the development of disorder. The various factors that causes the diabetes include; corporal immobility, sitting living way, smoking habits and use of wine. 55% diabetes is due the fatness. The higher fatness in youngsters in 1960-2000 was seen which causes the diabetes in those youngsters. The other factor which causes the

prevalence of diabetes type 2 is surroundings³. A chemical known as biphenyl A which is excreted through urine is present in plastic which sometime found to play a role in diabetes mellitus. The presence of diabetes in ancestors or other associations also causes the diabetes in the patients. If twins are produced from the same zygote then there are hundred percent chances that both will develop the disease if disease is present in their parents. Currently some genes were identified which are involved in the development of diabetes that include TFCFL2, PPARG, KCNJ11, WESI, JAZF1, CDKAL1 and HHEX.

These genes are involved in the appearance of proglucagon which further makes the glucagon. Fatness is also a genetic issue. Sometimes diabetes can as be progressed due to some clinical reasons. These include fatness, pressure, extra amount of fat and abnormality in chromosomes number. Some factors that enhance the chances of diabetes mellitus are older age, consumption of oily foods and consistency in life⁴.

Pathophysiology:

In the presence of diabetes, insulin is insensible and being opposed. The formation of insulin during the diabetes mellitus is lessened. Beta cells present in pancreases are destroyed when diabetes developed. During the diabetes mellitus less, glucose is elated towards liver, muscles and fat cells. More fat is degraded with hyperglycemia. There is a role of alpha cells in the diabetes type 2. This will cause the enhancements in the amounts of glucagon and hepatic beta cells that increased during fasting. It cannot be covered up with a banquet. Abnormal amount of insulin and enhanced insulin opposition resulted in hyperglycemia. Insulin can be excreted out from the blood by incretins⁵. For the treatment of the diabetes mellitus two procedures are made: GLP analog with enhanced partial subsists and DPP 4 inhibitors that avoids the collapse of endogenous GLP 1 as well as GIP. The purpose of both therapies is to regularize the fasting and better the functioning of beta cells presents in pancreas. Character of destruction of mitochondria in the progression of insulin opposition and analysis of type 2 diabetes is now under examination. The examination of fat cells is also significant⁶.

Most of the fatty persons are caught by diabetes mellitus. So fat cells have an important role in the development of diabetes. For the identification of association between this can be explained by portal supposition. Recently two more suppositions were formed to play a role between insulin opposition and dysfunctioning of type 2 diabetes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Transmission and identification:**

Investigations for transmission and identifications are present previously. The investigation for transmission and identification was similar. Optimistic partition is equal to the identification of pre diabetes condition. In 25% cases of diabetes an issue in the small vessels was seen before the identification of the diabetes. It means that they were showing the indications of diabetes from the last 5 years. The indications of the diabetes were suggested by American Diabetic Association and National diabetic group⁷. The indications of the diabetic patients are excess appetite and thirst and loss of weight. ADA suggested FPG for the identification of diabetes and WHO suggested OGTT for the identification of diabetes. To manage the glucose level in blood we still use glycated hemoglobin and fructosamine. But doctors also Experiment on other treatment method for cure. When the glucose level in the body is observed there is no separating lines which differentiate between the normal and diabetic individual. The IEC has designated to advocate a separating line for diabetes identification that focuses specificity, remarking that this is managed the disgrace and charge of incorrectly observing persons as diabetic alongside the minimal medical results of impeding the identification in a sufferer with an hemoglobin level < 6.5%.

Balancing:

We can manage the diabetes by improving quality of life and food⁸. By managing the body mass catalog to 25DM we observe an important decrease in the chances of type 2 diabetes. Other factors also reduce the diabetes which includes use of food greater in fat, physical workout, avoidance of smoking and wine intake. By improving the standard of life, we can improve the type 2 diabetes mellitus. A physical workout and standard of life is predicted by physicians for the patients to improve the diabetes type 2.

DISCUSSION:

Pharmacological agents:

Biguanides:

Biguanides is the most frequently used chemicals for the fatty patients of diabetes. It reduces the formation of glucose in the body. It enhances the compassion of the insulin. It also lessened the absorption of the glucose into the intestine⁹. In 2008, a report was in printed which express the role of metformin as a protein that is important in the hepatic gluconeogenesis genes. Metformin should be used with vigilance in older patients with mutilation of kidney because of concern of development of lactic acidosis.

Sulfonylurea:

This chemical is more accepted. It excites the emission of internal insulin. It can cause the

hypoglycemia. Older cases cured with sulfonylurea have 35% more chances to develop hypoglycemia as compared to younger cases of diabetes¹⁰. Greater chances of hypoglycemia developed due to Glyburide as compared to glipizide. Hypoglycemia developed due to older age, constant use of insulin, more than 60 years of age, currently liberated from the clinics, use of wine, use of many drugs for treatment etc. In older cases glyburide should not be utilized instead use of glipizide should be favored.

Meglitinides:

The two forms of the Meglitinides repaginate and nateglinide act as non-sulfonylurea secretagogues. They react on the K conduits which depend on the ATP in the beta cells of the pancreas. They force the pancreatic beta cells to liberate insulin. Meglitinides act rapidly and take less time for its action, so it decreases the chances of hypoglycemia. It is given to the patients before the eating of food. The purpose to give it before food is that the glucose could be controlled in the body. The site of formation of repaginate is kidney. It is formulated in larger amount in kidney but excreted in small amount with time to time.

Thiazolidinediones:

Thiazolidinediones is the predictor of insulin. The issue of insulin opposition by diabetes type 2 cases was initially detected by this drug. There is no link between pioglitazone and hypoglycemia. It is mostly utilized in the mutilation of kidney and easily accepted by elderly patients. However, it has some disadvantages like tangential edema, liquid preservation and chances of ruptures in females. Due to which it can never be used for the patients of diabetes whose age is greater. So, the use of pioglitazone is limited in older patients because it can cause the heart issues¹¹.

Alpha Glucosidase Inhibitors:

Acarbose, Voglibose and Miglitol are rarely used by the patients. But these are the secure and successful drugs for treatment of diabetic patients. These are mostly used for the treatment of hyperglycemia and not be used for the mutilation of kidney. It can cause dysentery and frugal so its use is restricted¹². The management of the glucose can be made by Volibose which is the recent medicine. It causes the late development of the disorder.

Insulin:

Insulin can be used separately or in amalgamation with hypoglycemic mediators. If some beta cells role remnants intensification therapy with basal insulin. If beta cell overtiredness happens, substitution of basal bolus insulin is important. In case of glucose poisonous substitution is significant using salvage operation. It should imitate the

standard discharge of insulin by the beta cells of pancreas. Insulin is injected in the body in the form of injections. It has various types some acts in a less duration of time and some acts greater duration of time. The kinds which act in small duration cause the greater chances of hypoglycemia as compared to the kinds which take longer duration of time for action¹³.

Insulin analog:

Insulin therapy has the capability to imitate the common physical emission of insulin. Conventional, transitional and extended performing insulin are inadequate by contradictory amalgamation and climaxes of achievements that may consequence in hypoglycemia. There is difference in the outlines of pharmacokinetic and new insulin. Their inception and time period taken for function are also different varied from speedy to protract.

Prospects in Drug Therapy Inhaled Insulin:

After the endorsement of European Medicines Evaluation Agency and FDA in 2006, insulin was presented for the use of common men¹⁴. It is the kind of insulin which acts on the patients with greater speed and can be used for the treatment of both type 1 and type 2 diabetic patients. It has been shown by the experiments that injection of insulin is as helpful but it is not significant than small performing insulin. In October 2007, it was presented commercially by first time.

Bromocriptine:

Recently an advanced method of treatment was developed for the diabetic patients. How this drug act on the patients is not clear so far¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

The diabetes type 2 can be managed and improved by changing the standard of life, modification in food, and organization of fatness. To aware the common masses are important to control the progressing contagion. Some special medicines are discovered, still there is no specific treatment obtainable. By enhancing the standard of existence, we can control the diabetes type 2.

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